

Development of the Rapid Flight Test Prototyping System for Unmanned Air Vehicles *

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Abstract

This paper describes the development of a rapid prototyping system for flight testing of guidance, navigation, and control algorithms for unmanned air vehicles. The system affords a small team the ability to take a new concept in guidance, navigation, and control from initial conception to flight test. In order to do this, a number of engineering problems had to be overcome addressing a gamut of issues including weight, power, portability, risk, electronic interference, vibration, manpower, etc. The main contribution of the paper is the proof of concept flight test demonstration of a new integrated guidance and control algorithm [1].

1 Introduction

Testing of a new algorithm, sensor package, vehicle, etc., requires expertise from many branches of the engineering sciences, especially aeronautic, electrical, and computer. It is costly and time consuming, as well as having the potential for catastrophic failure. When successfully done, however, it provides developmental information, insight and data that are unavailable from other sources.

The paper begins with a conceptual discussion of the Rapid Flight Test Prototyping System (RFTPS). Motivation for its development is addressed. Next, a description of the hardware components is given. The main contribution of the paper is discussed in the last section, where an application of the RFTPS to the problem of integrated guidance and control introduced in [1] is presented. The full capabilities of the RFTPS are demonstrated when this novel guidance algorithm is taken from theoretical development to flight test.

2 System Description

The RFTPS consists of a test bed unmanned air vehicle equipped with a complete avionics suite necessary for an autonomous flight as shown in Figure 1, and of a ground station responsible for flight control of the UAV and flight data collection as shown in Figure 2. A functional block diagram of the RFTPS is shown in Figure 3. The key goal was to use off-the-shelf-technology as much as possible, thus exploiting the economy of scale of a number of commercial industries. Furthermore, if the UAV development program is to span many years, and to draw on the talents of the NPS students in the future, the RFTPS

had to emphasize high level algorithm design. Low level code and device driver generation is kept to a minimum with the vast majority of the code "writing" being done via autocode tools. The system architecture is open, providing the ability to add, remove or change real time input/output (I/O). Computational power can be increased as mission requirements dictate. The telemetry links are secure, yet low power and unobtrusive to the public, not requiring advance permission for use, special frequencies from a government authority, or special airspace. The onboard components are light weight and low power, allowing for the inclusion of additional payload.

Figure 1: *Frog*: The unmanned air vehicle at the Naval Postgraduate School.

2.1 RFTPS Capabilities

The RFTPS developed provides the following capabilities: 1) within the RFTPS environment, one can synthesize, analyze and simulate guidance, navigation, control, and mission management algorithms using a high level development language. The same code that ran the simulation, flies the vehicle; 2) algorithms are seamlessly moved from the high level design and simulation environment to the real time processor; 3) the RFTPS utilizes industry standard I/O including digital to analog, analog to digital, serial, and pulse width modulation capabilities; 4) the RFTPS is portable, easily fitting in a car. In general, testing will occur at fields away from the immediate vicinity of the Naval Postgraduate School. 5) the unmanned air vehicle can be flown manually, autonomously, or using a combination of the two. For instance, automatic control of the lateral axis can be tested while the elevator and throttle are controlled manually; 6) all I/O and

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Figure 2: The base station of the RFTPS in use at the airfield.

internal algorithm variables can be monitored, collected and analyzed within the RFTPS environment.

2.2 Cost, Safety and Other Considerations

Cost and risk are two leading, and at times competing, concerns that had to be effectively handled. Since initial testing is to occur within line of sight at all times, a pulse width modulated (PWM) remote control system manufactured by Futaba was chosen. Testing of a new control algorithm is similar to handing over control of the aircraft to a student pilot. The algorithm should have full freedom to perform, yet adequate safeguards must exist in case it fails. With some modifications, the extensive master-slave flight training capabilities built in to the existing RC transmitters were exploited. A significant portion of the cost of the RFTPS resides in the real time processor, I/O board and modules, and in the host computer. Additionally, while compact, the weight and power requirements of these components are significant when compared to onboard power and payload available. In order to gain additional payload, and in order to manage the risk associated with the loss of an expensive computer package, the real time controller was kept on the ground. Sensor and control links to the real time controller were bridged via RF components described later.

2.3 Components

The centerpiece of the RFTPS ground station is the AC100/C30 system from Integrated Systems Incorporated. The key feature of this product is its autocode tools. With a relatively short time available for research by the NPS students, emphasis had to be shifted from code writing, debugging and maintenance to algorithm development. AC100/C30 utilizes "Xmath/SystemBuild", a graphical programming environment that uses a high level block diagram paradigm for modeling of linear and nonlinear systems. Within the "Xmath/SystemBuild" environment, the algorithm can be built, simulated, tested, and debugged. Real-time code can then be generated for execution on the real time processor.

Figure 3: RFTPS Hardware Architecture

Currently, the "Xmath/SystemBuild" environment resides on a Sun workstation. PC's running Windows NT are also supported. This allows for a significant downsizing of the ground station should resources become available in the future. Communication with the real time processor is via an Ethernet bus using TCP/IP protocol. AC100/C30 provides excellent animation tools for building graphical user interfaces (GUI). Through the appropriate design of these interfaces, the flight test team can monitor, modify, and control the actions of the real time processor. The GUI resides on the workstation. Communication between the workstation and the real time processor is via the Ethernet connection, and is managed by a host PC. Additionally, the host PC provides power to the real time processor, as well as providing utilities for compiling, linking, and downloading the C-code.

The I/O consists of four multi-mode, bi-directional, serial ports utilizing RS-232 protocol, a 16 channel pulse width modulation port capable of measuring up to sixteen PWM signals or generating up to six PWM signals, and a six channel digital-to-analog converter. The I/O modules are hosted by the same PC that holds the real time processor. The real time processor is a single Texas Instruments Digital Signal Processor (TMS320C30). The capability exists for upgrading the processor, or running multiple processors, to meet computational demands of future projects.

The control configuration of the air vehicle is conventional with three independent surfaces (elevator, aileron, rudder) and a throttle. Manual control is provided via a Futaba, dual conversion, PWM transmitter utilizing the portion of the radio spectrum reserved for Radio Controlled (RC) flight, 72.030 MHz to 72.990 MHz. Precautions entail a search of the electronic spectrum utilizing a hand held spectrum analyzer, as well as standard procedures employed by RC hobbyists to avoid two individuals selecting the same frequency locally. Built in capabilities of the transmitter include the ability to transmit one or more signals from a slave transmitter. The slave trans-

mitter is a modified Futaba transmitter where the manual control effectors have been replaced by a direct connection to the digital-to-analog I/O module. In this way, an exogenous source (RFTPS) can be given control of one, some, or all of the control actuators of the aircraft using the same RC link currently controlling the aircraft.

The sensor suite onboard the air vehicle consists of an inertial measurement unit (IMU) with a three axis rate gyro, three axis accelerometer, magnetic heading indicator, two axis pendulum, phase differential GPS receiver, elevator, aileron, and rudder actuator position sensors, and angle of attack, side-slip angle, pitot-static, and static pressure air data sensors. A four channel analog-to-digital converter is used to capture any four of the following sensors: elevator, aileron, rudder actuator position, angle of attack, side-slip angle, dynamic pressure, or static pressure.

Communication between the sensors and the real time processor is via a serial link. Low power, matched, spread spectrum RF links provide up to 115 Kbaud rates at over 10 miles range. They require no license, and can be used anywhere in the United States. Additionally, the onboard GPS unit maintains contact via a serial link with a GPS receiver on the ground, which provides differential corrections.

3 Trajectory Control: An Application

The intent of this application was to demonstrate the utility of the RFTPS by flight testing a new integrated guidance and control algorithm that was shown to have good performance and robustness properties both theoretically and in simulation [1]. This project was chosen because, on one hand, it is a totally unique application in terms of the guidance and control algorithms implemented. On the other hand, to implement this algorithm, most of the steps required of any application involving autonomous flight of an air vehicle must be accomplished. If done correctly, the foundation will be laid for follow on projects and joint ventures utilizing unmanned air vehicles.

Generic tasks fundamental to guidance, navigation and control algorithm development were accomplished first. To begin with, a high fidelity model of the test bed vehicle, nicknamed *Frog*, was developed. This involved a complete lateral and longitudinal parameter identification of *Frog's* stability and control derivatives. This led to the development of a six degree of freedom, nonlinear simulation. In order to manage the risk associated with the autonomous flight, it was decided to add an onboard inner-loop controller. The inner-loop controller modifies the vehicle dynamics such that displacements of the primary longitudinal and lateral control effectors correspond to various *trimming trajectories*, as defined in [1]. The inner-loop controller selected was a commercial autopilot whose control laws had to be identified as well. Additionally, accurate and timely calibration of the I/O needed to become an integral part of the RFTPS to account for changing environmental conditions, battery levels, etc.

This section discusses the process used to identify a model of *Frog*. First, the experimental testing completed to obtain data used in the parameter identification process is summarized. Flight test data is compared with the simulation results to demonstrate the efficacy of the effort. Then, a linear controller design based on modeling results obtained is discussed. Next, a nonlinear controller implementation based on the theory developed in

[1] is presented. Finally, flight tests conducted using the RFTPS to track an interesting representative trajectory are discussed. Data from flight tests is presented and contrasted with results from simulations. Along the way, implementation issues germane to the flight testing process are explained.

3.1 Vehicle Model Identification

The conventional configuration of *Frog* suggested that the parameter identification problem could be decoupled into longitudinal and lateral dynamics. Maximum likelihood parameter identification was used to refine existing analytic estimates of the longitudinal stability and control derivatives [3]. The results for a few key longitudinal stability derivatives are compared to analytic estimates in Table 1. The primary difference was in the estimate of the elevator effectiveness, which was less than half as effective as previously thought.

Derivative	Analytic	Experimental	% Δ
$C_{L\alpha}$	4.30	4.09	5.13
$C_{M\alpha}$	-0.417	-0.557	-25.1
$C_{L\delta_e}$	-1.12	-0.391	186
$C_{M\delta_e}$	-1.62	-1.05	54.3

Table 1: Comparison of selected longitudinal derivatives.

Figure 4 shows the response, in simulation, of a longitudinal model of *Frog* using these derivatives to an elevator doublet. Comparisons are made to the results from flight test.

Figure 4: An elevator doublet is used to excite the longitudinal dynamics of *Frog*. Test flight data is compared with simulation results to assess validity of the model.

Same process was repeated for the lateral axis. Aileron and rudder doublets were executed while aileron and rudder position, roll and yaw rates, and side-slip angle were measured. Results, for a few key lateral stability derivatives, are compared to analytic estimates in Table 2.

3.2 Autopilot Model Identification

The inner-loop autopilot is a "black box" containing both sensors and controller logic. The intent was to model the unit as closely as possible without disassembling it. Autopilot's function is to control vertical speed and turn

Derivative	Analytic	Experimental	% Δ
$C_{Y\beta}$	-.310	-.987	-68.6
$C_{l\beta}$	-.051	-.094	-45.7
$C_{N\beta}$.058	.176	-67.0
$C_{l\delta_a}$.181	.239	-24.3

Table 2: Comparison of selected lateral derivatives.

rate of the aircraft. This naturally decouples into an identification problem for the lateral channel, and an identification problem for the longitudinal channel.

The lateral channel employs a rate gyro to track turn rate commands via feedback to the aileron. Parameter identification algorithms were used to determine that the rate gyro feedback loop could be approximated by the following transfer function: $T_1 = \frac{-1s+1}{s+1}$.

With the autopilot on, a step command in turn rate was transmitted to the vehicle in flight. Vehicle turn rate, as measured by the IMU, was recorded and used to estimate the value of the feedforward gain in the lateral channel K_{lat} at 0.25. Test data from that flight is shown in Figure 5 and compared with simulation results using the autopilot model.

Figure 5: Flight test data is used to identify the dynamics of the autopilot. A step signal is sent to the lateral channel of the autopilot. Measured yaw rate is compared to simulation results.

The longitudinal channel of the autopilot senses the rate of change of static pressure in order to control the vehicle's vertical velocity via feedback to the elevator. Flight tests data capturing the response of the vehicle to a step input in climb rate command was used for model identification. With accurate models of *Frog* and of the onboard autopilot identified, it was a simple matter to determine the command bandwidths of the inner-loop controller. For this project, this would be the limiting factor in achievable performance of the guidance algorithm. Hardware-in-the-loop testing of the actuators found their bandwidth to be an order of magnitude higher than the inner-loop command bandwidths. A natural next step would be to remove the autopilot after sufficient time and experience have reduced the risk exposure to acceptable levels, and exploit the extra actuator bandwidth available.

3.3 Design of the Controller

The design requirements to be met were as included typical tracking requirements, bandwidth requirements, closed loop damping and stability margins as well as following implementation requirements: 1) control of *Frog* from the console, open-loop, must be possible in order to maneuver the vehicle to a suitable location overhead the field based on visual cues and displayed navigational data; 2) switching from open-loop control to autonomous flight should be accomplished from the console at the discretion of the console operator. The switch should be *bumpless* with no undesirable transients; 3) the definition of the inertial trajectory passed to the controller should be easily defined from the console, and expressed in terms of the parameters introduced in [1], namely, helix angle (γ_c), radius (b_c), and turn rate (ψ_c). The synthesis of the controller represents an application of the results outlined in [1], where a method is derived for the design of a nonlinear gain-scheduled controller to track so-called trimming trajectories with guaranteed local stability and robustness properties.

4 Results and Analysis

This section summarizes the results of the flight test of the guidance and control algorithm developed in the preceding section. The flight took place at approximately 500 feet of altitude above ground level. Wind measurements were made at ground level on the runway, and later incorporated into the simulation. The pilot maintained control of the throttle throughout the tests. During autonomous flight, the pilot left the throttle at the trim setting for the trajectory defined. The rudder was not used.

The resulting path in space flown is shown in Figure 7. It is compared to the reference trajectory. The projection of the trajectory tracked onto the horizontal plane is shown in Figure 6. It, also, is compared to results from simulation. The history of the controller activity is shown for the lateral channel in Figure 8, and for the longitudinal channel in Figure 9.

Figure 6: Autonomous flight test of *Frog*. Trajectory tracking: 2D view.

With little wind, the test data characterizes the performance of the guidance and control algorithm in the presence of modeling errors, transport lag, hardware nonlinearities, and sensor noise. The simulation results were a close match to flight test data along the lateral channel. The average tracking error was just over 21 feet. It can

Figure 7: Autonomous flight of *Frog*. Trajectory tracking: 3D view.

Figure 8: Top graph: Commanded vehicle yaw rate, in degrees per second from the controller, along the trajectory flown. Bottom graph: Lateral error in feet, as computed by the guidance algorithm, along the same trajectory.

be seen in Figure 8 that the integral control is holding about one half degree per second commanded yaw rate to compensate for constant disturbances. In flight, tracking errors along the longitudinal channel were even less than lateral tracking errors. The average command signal along the longitudinal channel was -5 feet per second. This probably indicates that the power setting was too high. Subsequent testing will incorporate airspeed and throttle control which will address this issue. In simulation, however, longitudinal tracking errors were extremely small. The discrepancy is most likely the result of unmodeled vertical disturbances in the airmass due to light thermal activity.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, an integrated system for the design, development and testing of guidance, navigation, and control algorithms for unmanned air vehicles was presented. Extensive use was made of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) hardware. This kept costs low, and made the system easily scaleable. Sophisticated autocode tools allowed a two man team to write, test, and maintain thousands of lines of error-free real time code. In a single, unified environment, the avionics system was designed, simulated, simulated incorporating hardware-in-the-loop

Figure 9: The output of the longitudinal channel of the controller is shown along with the error signal on which it is acting. Note that the positive z -axis points down and that positive error corresponds to the vehicle being below the reference trajectory.

(HITL), tested in flight, and used to control an aircraft in flight.

As a proof-of-concept demonstration, the RFTPS was used to take the integrated guidance and control concept presented in [1] and evaluate it in the environment for which it was proposed to be used. The project began with an unmanned air vehicle with unknown flight characteristics. In addition, a "black box" autopilot with unknown internal dynamics was placed onboard the vehicle. Through the use of the RFTPS, a high fidelity simulation of the vehicle and autopilot was built and used to synthesize the applicable guidance and control laws. Extensive testing in simulation followed, and appropriate user interfaces were developed. Then, the RFTPS was used to control the vehicle in flight using the guidance and control laws developed, collect the data during the flight test, post process the data, and evaluate the performance of the algorithms.

The success of the project demonstrated both the utility of the integrated guidance and control algorithm as well as the capabilities of the RFTPS. The integrated guidance and control algorithm was shown to work well in a real world application. Performance in flight was very close to performance in simulation, which speaks well of the robustness properties of the controller. Changing environmental conditions highlighted some disturbance rejection issues that should be addressed in the future. The RFTPS was shown to be powerful, portable, rugged, effective in the field and in the lab, and safe and reliable at controlling an aircraft.

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